

Unlocking the archives

A pipeline for scanning, indexing, transcribing, and modelling entities of archival documents into Linked Open Data

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Keywords

Entity Extraction from Archival Documents, GLAM, Linked Open Data, Dutch Golden Age

Abstract

In the project *Golden Agents: Creative Industries and the Making of the Dutch Golden Age*, heterogeneous resources on the production of the creative industries in the Dutch Golden Age from heritage institutions (e.g. Rijksmuseum, KB, RKD) are brought together as linked data. Added to this, the digitization of the enormously rich collection of the notarial deeds in the Amsterdam City Archives will provide data on the consumption of cultural goods by the inhabitants of all layers of society in Amsterdam during the Dutch Golden Age. This archive currently plays a pioneering role in the massive digitization process of archival inventories. In the project *Alle*

Amsterdams Akten [All Amsterdam Deeds] handwritten notarial deeds are indexed on the level of inventories, documents, person names, and geolocations outside Amsterdam. At the same time, the full text of these documents is being made searchable by using the advanced Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) tool Transkribus in the project *Crowd Leert Computer Lezen* [Crowd Teaches the Computer how to Read] in combination with corrections of the transcriptions by volunteers.

In the Golden Agents project, novel ways are explored to extract all entities of objects that are mentioned in such notary deeds between 1578 and 1750 that are relevant to get insight into the cultural goods of Amsterdammers in the Dutch Golden Age. TICCLAT (Reynaert et al. 2019) is used to find and extract these object entities, and once extracted and identified, almost all types of these objects can be linked to thesauri such as the Getty's Art & Architecture Thesaurus [AAT] and reconciled with textual/linguistic references to an item in an external (authored) dataset, such as the STCN, ICONCLASS, and those of the RKD. The development of the model that is used to express the combined, enriched, and created data is still work in progress. It will be compliant with major and widely used data models in the Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAM) world, such as the CIDOC-CRM.

Here the full pipeline from archives to annotations is represented (Figure 1) that comprehends the successive stages of scanning, indexing, transcribing, correcting, aggregating, and modelling the entities of archival documents into RDF as Linked Open Data. It provides the creation of transparent datasets that can be replicated, evaluated and used for quantitative analyses in digital humanities research. Subsequently, Figure 2 and Figure 3 show a simplified RDF representation of a textual reference to a painting and a book as can be found in probate inventories.

These two examples show how references to objects in archival documents can be connected to external thesauri and datasets while keeping the provenance chain by pointing back to their location in the archival document. The same principle applies to other entity types, such as persons and locations. Besides connecting the entity to an external (authored) dataset (e.g. ECARTICO or ULAN), disambiguating the entity within the Amsterdam City Archives dataset can also be a next step. Within the Golden Agents projects, the Lenticular Lenses (Idrissou et al. 2018) tool is used for this.

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Figure 1 - Flowchart of the pipeline

←oa:hasSelector/foaf:depiction

Figure 2 - Simplified RDF representation of a reference to a painting

Figure 3 - Simplified representation of a reference to a book/poem